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Review Article

AN OVERVIEW OF HERBAL COSMETICS**Arun.V.Kambale¹, Rohan.G.Ajabe², Vinayak.A.Katekar³, Yashkumar.R.Dhole⁴
,Dr. Swati.P.Deshmukh⁵**^{1,2}.Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.³. Department of Quality Assurance, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India^{4,5}.Department of Pharmacolgy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra ,India.**Abstract:**

Herbal cosmetics are preferred by consumers because they are more effective, more useful and have fewer side effects. Their ability to treat many skin conditions, soften the skin and improve its appearance is well known. This herb has antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant and anthelmintic properties, helps heal wounds and protects the skin. Cosmetics are the fastest growing personal care products and are cosmetics that contain bioactive ingredients or ingredients of natural origin. In recent years, the demand for the use of medicinal plants in cosmetics has been increasing because they are less painful, non-toxic and more effective. People's desire to look good and beautiful has opened a huge market for cosmetics. Nowadays, people's desire to be younger, more beautiful, fresher, attractive and fairer than their actual age has directly increased the market demand for herbal cosmetics and lotions. Therefore, the use of herbal cosmetics and cosmeceuticals is ignored in the review. He also describes plants as cosmetics. It may be essential for beauty and skin care.

Keywords: Herbal cosmetics; antioxidant; anti-Inflammatory; anti-aging; skin cosmetics; hair cosmetics ; tooth cosmetics.

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INTRODUCTION:

Over the years, the use of herbal ingredients in cosmetics has evolved, and today, these products are formulated using advanced techniques to ensure maximum effectiveness. Herbal cosmetics are beauty and skincare products that are made using natural ingredients derived from plants, herbs, and other botanical sources. These products are gaining popularity due to their numerous benefits and the increasing demand for natural and organic skincare solutions. One of the key advantages of herbal cosmetics is that they are free from harsh chemicals, synthetic fragrances, and artificial colors that are commonly found in conventional cosmetics. Herbal cosmetics offer a wide range of benefits for the skin and hair. Many herbs and plants have natural healing properties that can help to soothe and nourish the skin, promote cell regeneration, and improve overall skin health. For example, aloe vera is known for its moisturizing and anti-inflammatory properties, while tea tree oil has antibacterial and antifungal properties that can help to treat acne and other skin conditions. In addition to their skincare benefits, herbal cosmetics are also environmentally friendly.

How to use herbs?

Dried herbs are best used in oil (or butter, shortening) or water; In this way they can be converted into oil or liquid. Don't forget to crush the herbs with your fingers or sauté them a bit to make them swell. Grinding a batch with a mortar and pestle also works. I like to use dried herbs more when I use them. Plants have been used for thousands of years to add flavor to food, to make medicine and to cook. If you find the food is low in fat or low in salt, use herbs to improve the flavor of almost any dish, including desserts. Herbs are often available dried or fresh and are easy to use. Herbs, leaves and green parts of plants (seeds, barks, roots).

Advantages of herbal cosmetics over synthetic

Following are some of the advantages of using natural cosmetics which make them a better choice over the synthetic ones:

1.Natural Products

The name indicates that herbal cosmetics are natural and do not contain all the harmful synthetic chemicals that can be toxic to the skin. In this product, different plants and plant extracts are used instead of synthetic products such as aloe vera gel and coconut oil. They also contain natural ingredients like vitamin E to keep your skin healthy and beautiful. For example, Aloe vera is a herbal plant species belonging to liliaceae family and is naturally and easily available .

There are a rising number of consumers concerned about ingredients such as synthetic chemicals, mineral oils who demand more natural products with traceable and more natural ingredients, free from harmful chemicals and with an emphasis on the properties of botanicals.

2.Safety of use

Compared with other beauty products, natural cosmetics are safe to use. They are hypoallergenic, dermatologist tested and proven, and can be used safely anytime, anywhere. Since they are made from natural ingredients, people do not need to worry about rashes or skin irritation. Hydroxyanisole and BHA (butylated hydroxytoluene) are similar antiseptics and are used as antiseptics in lip balms and moisturizers. BHA and BHT can cause allergic reactions on the skin. The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified BHA as carcinogenic to humans. Herbal cosmetics contain natural antioxidants such as vitamin C.

3.Not Tested on Animals

Some cosmetics are first tested on animals to ensure they are safe and effective for humans. But natural cosmetics do not need to be tested on animals. These natural formulas are tested in the laboratory by experts with state-of-the-art equipment and do not contain any animals.

4.No side effect

Synthetic beauty products have many side effects. They can clog pores, cause irritation, and make the skin dry or oily, but herbal products do not have these effects. Additionally, herbal products do not contain parabens, which often cause side effects. In addition, since they are produced from natural products, they do not harm the body. They cleanse the skin without causing any harm.

5.Economical to use

Commercial use of natural cosmetics is not expensive. Some of these products are even cheaper than synthetic products. They are available at a discount and sold at a cheap price during sales. Sufficient research time is required to find good results. Estimates from the World Health Organization show that due to the side effects and rising costs of modern medicine, approximately 80% of the world's population relies on natural, clean products for their health care. The World Health Organization now recommends and encourages the use of herbal medicines in health plans because they are cheap and safe.

Classification of herbal cosmetics

Skin Care Products:

- Cleansers and Toners: Herbal cleansers often include ingredients like aloe vera, neem, and turmeric for gentle cleansing.
- Moisturizers: Aloe vera, chamomile, and calendula are common in herbal moisturizers for hydration.
- Anti-Aging Creams: Ginseng, green tea, and licorice may be used for their antioxidant properties.
- Sunscreen: Herbal sunscreens may contain extracts like aloe vera, carrot seed oil, or green tea for natural sun protection.

Hair Care Products:

- Shampoos: Herbal shampoos use ingredients such as hibiscus, amla, and bhringraj for nourishing hair.
- Conditioners: Herbal conditioners often incorporate ingredients like fenugreek, coconut oil, and aloe vera.
- Hair Oils: Ayurvedic herbs like brahmi, amla, and hibiscus are common in herbal hair oils.

Makeup:

- Foundation and BB Creams: Herbal makeup products may include natural pigments like beetroot, turmeric, or mica.
- Lipsticks and Lip Balms: Beeswax, shea butter, and herbal extracts provide moisture and color.
- Eyeliners and Mascara: Charcoal, almond oil, and aloe vera are often used in herbal eyeliners and mascaras.

Fragrances:

- Perfumes: Herbal perfumes utilize essential oils from plants like lavender, rose, and jasmine for a natural scent.
- Deodorants: Ingredients like tea tree oil, sage, and chamomile are used for their antibacterial properties.
- Personal Care and Hygiene:
- Toothpaste: Herbal toothpaste may contain neem, clove, and mint for oral health.
- Soaps: Ingredients like sandalwood, turmeric, and neem are common in herbal soaps.

Therapeutic Products:

- Acne Treatments: Herbal ingredients like tea tree oil, neem, and turmeric are known for their anti-acne properties.

- Herbal Masks and Scrubs: Ingredients like clay, oats, and herbal extracts are used for exfoliation and rejuvenation.

Health Supplements:

- Herbal Capsules and Tablets: Ginseng, ginkgo biloba, and turmeric are often used in herbal supplements for various health benefits.
- Herbal Teas: Chamomile, peppermint, and ginger are common in herbal teas for promoting wellness.

Body Care:

- Body Lotions: Herbal body lotions may contain ingredients like aloe vera, cocoa butter, and calendula for skin nourishment.
- Massage Oils: Ayurvedic herbs like ashwagandha and sesame oil are used in herbal massage oils.
- Remember, the effectiveness of herbal cosmetics can vary, and it's essential to choose products that align with your skin type and specific needs. Always check ingredient lists for potential allergens.

Raw Materials Generally Used In herbal Cosmetics

Herbal cosmetics utilize a variety of raw materials derived from plants and natural sources. Common ingredients include:

1. **Botanical Extracts:** Extracts from plants like aloe vera, chamomile, green tea, and calendula provide soothing and anti-inflammatory properties.
2. **Herbs and Spices:** Turmeric, neem, rosemary, and lavender are often incorporated for their antibacterial and antioxidant qualities.
3. **Carrier Oils:** Coconut oil, jojoba oil, and olive oil are frequently used as base oils for their moisturizing and nourishing effects.
4. **Essential Oils:** Extracts from plants such as lavender, tea tree, peppermint, and eucalyptus contribute fragrance and therapeutic benefits.
5. **Fruit Extracts:** Fruits like papaya, orange, and lemon provide natural acids and vitamins that promote skin radiance and rejuvenation.
6. **Clays and Mud:** Kaolin clay, bentonite, and various muds are used for their cleansing and detoxifying properties.
7. **Honey:** Known for its moisturizing and antibacterial properties, honey is a common ingredient in herbal skincare products.
8. **Seeds and Nuts:** Ingredients like almond, argan, and shea butter are rich sources of fatty acids, providing hydration and nourishment.

9. **Floral Waters:** Hydrosols like rose water and lavender water add a gentle and aromatic touch to herbal cosmetics.
10. **Natural Waxes:** Beeswax and carnauba wax are used for texture and consistency in products like balms and creams.

Herbal Plants For Treatment Of Various Elements

1. **Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*):** Known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, turmeric has been used to alleviate conditions like arthritis and promote overall well-being.
2. **Peppermint (*Mentha × piperita*):** Often used for digestive issues, peppermint can help with indigestion, bloating, and irritable bowel syndrome (IBS).
3. **Aloe Vera (*Aloe barbadensis miller*):** Renowned for its soothing properties, aloe vera is commonly used for skin conditions like burns, sunburns, and dermatitis.
4. **Echinacea (*Echinacea purpurea*):** Thought to enhance the immune system, echinacea is often used to prevent or treat colds and respiratory infections.
5. **Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*):** Known for its anti-nausea and anti-inflammatory properties, ginger is often used to relieve nausea, motion sickness, and muscle soreness.
6. **Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*):** Recognized for its calming effects, lavender is used in aromatherapy to reduce stress and improve sleep.
7. **Garlic (*Allium sativum*):** With antimicrobial properties, garlic is believed to boost the immune system and contribute to cardiovascular health.

CONCLUSION:

Herbal cosmetics are beauty products made from plant extracts and natural ingredients. They aim to enhance skin and hair health without relying on synthetic chemicals. These products often include herbs, essential oils, and botanical extracts known for their therapeutic properties. Herbal cosmetics are promoted as a more natural and sustainable alternative to conventional beauty products, emphasizing the benefits of plant-based ingredients for skincare and beauty routines.

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